

EFFECTIVE ORGANIZATION OF SCHOOL LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the issues of effective organization and conduct of classes in educational institutions. The possibilities of pedagogical programs and technologies used in the course of the lesson are also revealed.

Key words: lessons, informatics, effective, iSpring, CourseLab, HotPotatoes, QuizMaker and PowerPoint, 3D book

ЭФФЕКТИВНАЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯ ШКОЛЬНЫХ УРОКОВ

Аннотация: В данной статье рассмотрены вопросы эффективной организации и проведения занятий в образовательных учреждениях. Также раскрыты возможности педагогических программ и технологий, применяемых в процессе урока.

Ключевые слова: уроки, информатика, эффективные, iSpring, CourseLab, HotPotatoes, QuizMaker and PowerPoint, 3D book

MAKTAB DARSLARINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim muassasalarida darslarni samarali tashkil qilish va uni o'tkazish bo'yicha fikr mulohazalar yuritilgan. Shuningdek, dars jarayonida qo'laniladigan pedagogic dasturlar va texnologiyalarning imkoniyatlar ochib berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: darslar, informatika, samarali, iSpring, CourseLab, HotPotatoes, QuizMaker and PowerPoint, 3D book

Introduction. Today, it is important to effectively organize lessons for schoolchildren. The reason is that in the era of developing technologies, it is one of the tasks of modern teachers to maintain and increase the interest of students in science, to help them become worthy professions in the future. I think that it is appropriate to use modern methods and certainly technologies in the organization of lessons. In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to the psychology of students. In addition, it is important for the student that the teacher can be like a parent and a close friend for each student.

As for the organization of lessons, I think that trying to organize each lesson perfectly is a great light on light. Because, as I said above, working with each student means 20 students in one class, 20 psychological worlds and behaviors. -means that there is a character. For example, a child may have an average upbringing, that is, he may talk loudly in class, but instead of reprimanding him or complaining to his parents, he should pay more attention to him and engage in individual activities. explaining the topic will be the right solution. The reason is that students who need attention behave like this in classes.

A lesson is an orderly activity of teachers and students aimed at one goal. If the student is not ready for the lesson, that is, he does not have the passion, desire to learn and does not like you, no matter how much you try, you will not achieve any result. Or the students are eager to learn, but the teacher is not ready for the lesson, there is no need to talk about the results of the lesson even if his mood or health does not allow it. Therefore, in order for the lesson to be effective, the goals and aspirations of both parties must be common. Therefore, it is necessary for every teacher to enter the lesson thoroughly prepared, with a good mood, and to observe the readiness of his students for the lesson, to be able to direct their attention and memories to the lesson, and to attract them to the lesson. For this, the teacher should organize the lesson taking into account the psychological and physical conditions of the students.

Our observations show that most of our teachers start the lesson as soon as they enter the class without taking into account the readiness of the students to listen to the lesson. It cannot be said that the result of such a lesson will be satisfactory. It would be correct to say that this is where the lesson begins.

Today's task of education is to teach students to be able to perform independent activities in the conditions of the information-educational environment that is increasing day by day, to effectively use modern information technologies in various fields and to use the flow of information wisely, to facilitate the teaching of lessons. It is to be able to master and apply their content in life, to achieve full mastery of all science programs. Nowadays, teachers of informatics, like all subjects, are required to use advanced pedagogical technologies, such as organizing lessons based on modern pedagogical requirements, using innovative approaches to lessons, teaching students to think independently during lessons. Interactive method - by increasing the activity between students and the teacher in the educational process, it serves to activate the learning of students and develop their personal qualities. Interactive (interactive) is an English word, "interact" - "inter" means mutual, "act" - means to act.

During the lesson, it is necessary to encourage the use of new methods, the integration of modern information technologies and, most importantly, to raise the morale of students. It is the task of skilled pedagogues to thoroughly research these. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich "For this purpose, the most important task of the relevant government agencies and the entire education system, respected professors and teachers is to provide a thorough education to the young generation, to raise them to be physically and spiritually mature people."

To date, the most used modern pedagogical programs in the educational process are: iSpring, CourseLab, HotPotatoes, QuizMaker, and PowerPoint. creating courses and Flash-presentations (iSpring Pro) "Science and Education" provides an opportunity to develop interactive tests, surveys and questionnaires. The simplest and most qualitative way to check the student's knowledge is created using the iSpring

QuizMaker program, which is an assessment test. In the iSpring program, you can create a 3D book, you can also create interactive elements of a glossary or a catalog. Any version of the program can be installed on our computer and an electronic course can be organized. CourseLab software capabilities: CourseLab 2.0 is certified for compliance with the SCORM 2004 standard, compliance level: CP SCORM 2004 Conformant, using CourseLab software does not require the user to know HTML or programming languages; An open object interface makes it easy to extend libraries of user-created objects and templates; The ability to show videos in different formats and insert audios for objective animation, the use of the above-mentioned pedagogical software tools in the course of education serves to increase the quality of education and increase the interactivity of education based on innovative technologies.

There are many methods and methods of making students interested in the lesson and motivating them. For this, a lot of life experience, skills, knowledge and aspiration are required from the teacher. The teaching methods are chosen depending on the aspirations, interests and psychology of the students of the class, and the teacher uses his own methods.

Teaching method refers to a set of measures and actions used by the teacher to overcome a certain obstacle that appears in the achievement of lesson goals.

Two teachers implement the same method, for example, brainstorming, in different ways. In order to attract the children to the lesson, one teacher speaks gently and in a low voice, while the other speaks loudly and shouts. When someone tells a story, the other reprimands and scolds. This variety is called style. The style cannot be written into the lesson outline, it appears during the course of the lesson.

It is very difficult to impress children today. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher not to be restless, to regularly read and learn innovative, non-traditional, interactive teaching methods and to be able to apply them to the educational process. The teacher should pay special attention to the artistic, aesthetic, logical, physical and spiritual development of students during the lesson. Let the student see, listen, speak,

observe, and write in one lesson. According to the analyzes conducted by our pedagogic psychologists, after 2 weeks, 10 percent of the information learned by the students is through independent reading, 20 percent through listening, and 30 percent through viewing. 50% will be remembered if he/she demonstrates or talks about it, 80% will be remembered through discussion and conversation, and 90% will be remembered if he/she does it practically. Taking this into account, we should conduct more debates, conversations and practical work under our observation and control during the lesson when teaching students.

The conclusion is that the use of new technologies in educational institutions is the need of the hour, but at the moment not all educational institutions have the same opportunity. Some educational institutions are not provided with computer equipment, some are not connected to the Internet. On the basis of the relevant decrees of our Honorable President Shavkat Mirziyoyev Miromonovich, equal opportunities are being created in all regions. This is certainly a good thing. Where there is education, there is growth. As they say, the best investment is in your education.

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